

JOHN STEINBECK: THE LITERARY TITAN AND HIS ENDURING LEGACY

Qodirova Maftuna Davron qizi

UzSWLU, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

missdove93@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10972859>

Abstract: This article examines the life and literary achievements of literary titan John Steinbeck, whose influence on literature is still felt today. We examine the enduring legacy of this legendary writer and his place in the literary canon by focusing on Steinbeck's remarkable work, his unique writing style, and the lasting impact of his pieces. We will examine Steinbeck's lasting influence on American literature and its application to contemporary culture through his narrative strategies, themes, and social criticism.

Keywords: *literary titan, Pulitzer Prize for Fiction, The Nobel prize for Literature, social criticism, Stream of Consciousness, literary innovator.*

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются жизнь и литературные достижения литературного титана Джона Стейнбека, влияние которого на литературу ощущается и сегодня. Мы исследуем непреходящее наследие этого легендарного писателя и его место в литературном каноне, сосредоточив внимание на замечательных работах Стейнбека, его уникальном стиле письма и непреходящем влиянии его произведений. Мы рассмотрим длительное влияние Стейнбека на американскую литературу и его применение в современной культуре через его повествовательные стратегии, темы и социальную критику.

Ключевые слова: литературный титан, Пулитцеровская премия по художественной литературе, Нобелевская премия по литературе, социальная критика, Поток сознания, литературный новатор.

Introduction. Few names stand out in the broad expanse of American literature like John Steinbeck's. With his unrivaled narrative powers, profound insights into the human condition, and steadfast devotion to social criticism, Steinbeck is regarded as a literary titan whose works have left an everlasting effect on the literary world. The amazing legacy of John Steinbeck is examined in this paper which emphasizes his stature as a literary giant whose works continue to be appreciated by readers of all ages. John Steinbeck tackles a wide range of social and political topics of his day in his books, which are renowned for their potent social criticism. For instance, his famous works "The Grapes of Wrath" (1939), "Of Mice and Men" (1937), "Cannery Row" (1945), "The Pearl" (1947) prompted readers to consider the social structures and beliefs that

support inequality from a critical perspective. For his remarkable works, especially for his masterpiece "The Grapes of Wrath" Steinbeck was awarded by *Pulitzer Prize for Fiction* in 1940 and *The Nobel prize for Literature* in 1962.

Main part. John Ernst Steinbeck, (February 27, 1902 - December 20, 1968) a prominent figure in American literature, was a writer of novels, short stories, social criticism, and war reporter during his age. Steinbeck's mother, Olive Hamilton, a former school teacher, instilled in her son an interest in literature from a young age.

In 1930, Steinbeck wrote "Murder at Full Moon", a detective story about a werewolf murder, but it was never published because Steinbeck did not think it was worthy of publication. [Sam S, July 27, 2021]. "Cup of Gold", Steinbeck's first novel and lone piece of historical fiction, tells the violent and fascinating narrative of the legendary pirate Henry Morgan. This book, published in 1929, served as the foundation for his entry into the realm of fiction. In addition to this work, his professional literary career began in 1932 with the release of "The Pastures of Heaven", a collection of stories set in the Salinas Valley and dedicated to his parents. [Wagner-Martin L, 2017]

In 1940, Steinbeck traveled to the Sea of Cortez with his friend Ed Ricketts, a marine scientist. Following the expedition, the two released a trip report titled *Sea of Cortez*, which featured a list of Ricketts' new species and a narrative by Steinbeck. Following Ricketts' death in 1948, Steinbeck republished the work as "The Journal from the Sea of Cortez". [Taylor A, 2023] Lindsey Hutton portrays imaginary characters like Steinbeck and his companion Ed Ricketts in "Monterey Bay" (2016), a book about the establishment of the Monterey Eye Aquarium. [Penguin Press, 2016]

Steinbeck's first critical breakthrough was "Tortilla Flat", a California Commonwealth Club Gold Medal winner set in postwar Monterey, California. It follows the exploits of a gang of impoverished and homeless young men in Monterey following World War I, just before the end of the American experience. [Parini J, 1996.]

"Travels with Charlie: In Search of America" recounts Steinbeck's 1960 expedition with his dog Charlie. In it, the author laments his lost childhood and ancestry while criticizing and appreciating the United States. According to the words of his son, Thomas, Steinbeck realized that he was about to die, so he went on a vacation to see this location for the last time. [Steinbeck Thom, 2007]

American author John Steinbeck was noted for his realistic and socially conscious books. His works frequently represent the lives of ordinary people,

particularly those who endured the financial challenges of the Great Depression. Steinbeck illuminated the human condition by delving into subjects such as poverty, injustice, and the endurance of the human spirit. The following significant features of Steinbeck's literary style may be identified:

- *Stream of Consciousness*: Steinbeck employed the stream-of-consciousness narrative approach to explore his characters' inner thoughts and feelings. ("The Grapes of Wrath");
- *Descriptive Language*: Steinbeck's writing style featured rich and vivid descriptions;
- *Characteristics*: Steinbeck was a talented writer who could build complicated, memorable characters;
- *Allegory and symbolism*: He frequently employed symbolic motifs in his works to convey larger ideas and themes. ("The Grapes of Wrath," "Of Mice and Men," and "Travels with Charlie: In Search of America")
- *Easy, conversational language*: To portray the authenticity of his characters' emotions, he often employed dialects and vernacular. ("The Grapes of Wrath" , "Cannery Row")
- *A social critic and supporter of justice*. Steinbeck's novels frequently have a strong sense of societal critique.
- *Chronicler of the American experience*: Steinbeck's writing masterfully captures the core of the American experience, particularly the Great Depression and its destruction. "The Grapes of Wrath", "Of Mice and Men"
- *Literary Innovator*: John Steinbeck invented narrative techniques and literary styles, combining vivid imagery, dialogue, and symbolism to create a distinct style that grabbed readers.

The writer received the Pulitzer Prize in 1940 for his masterwork "The Grapes of Wrath", followed by the Nobel Prize in Literature in 1962. The award praised his realistic and inventive writings, which combine incisive social insight, expressive characterisation, and a caring attitude toward people. The Nobel Prize solidified his reputation as a literary titan and expanded his impact on American writing.

Conclusion. Steinbeck's literary career is well-known for his new narrative approach and techniques, literary styles featured by descriptive language and memorable characters. Steinbeck's works depict ordinary people, particularly those affected by the Great Depression, highlighting issues like poverty, injustice, and the human spirit's endurance. Steinbeck's works have significantly

shaped and influenced future generations of writers, demonstrating their cultural permanence and lasting impact.

References:

1. Taylor Anne, Jul 25, 2023. 12 Novel Facts About John Steinbeck. <https://www.mentalfloss.com/>
2. "Penguin Press – Penguin Books USA". Archived from the original on December 20, 2016.
3. Parini Jay, 1996. John Steinbeck: A Biography. Holt Publishing & Co, 535 pages.
4. Sam Scott (July 27, 2021). "Beast of Eden". Stanford Magazine.
5. Thom Steinbeck, Archived September 27, 2007, at archive.today, September 13, 2006. Steinbeck knew he was dying. Audio interview with Thom Steinbeck.
6. Wagner-Martin Linda, 2017. John Steinbeck: A Literary Life. Palgrave Macmillan UK, 183 pages.